

Influential Role of Social Media' Travel Reviews in Trip Planning Decisions of Domestic Tourists in India

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Abstract : *Social media's role in travellers' trip planning processes is crucial. Travellers generally utilise user-generated content to reduce travel risk, which impacts their travel plans. The purpose of this research paper is to investigate the impact of social media's reviews on Indian tourists' trip planning. Also, the general trip-planning behaviour of Indian travelers has been studied. The study has examined the divergence of social media demand-and-supply patterns in India and social media usage for trip planning and their impact on Indian travellers travel plans. Descriptive Analysis, Exploratory Factor Analysis, and Logistic Regression techniques have been followed. It has been stated that people look for information on social media related to accommodations when travellers have already decided on a destination. The reason-result link of the travel review for trip planning has predicted travel review significance predictors, which caused tourists to modify their trip plans.*

Keywords : Social Media, Travel Planning Process, Online Travel Reviews, Information Sources, Trip Planning Stages.

Introduction

People use information and communication technology (ICT) to search for, organize, share, and create material on online platforms, which has progressed from a broadcast source to a public network (Parra-Lopez et al., 2011). Tourism is one of the key industries in many cities and the primary force of economic development (Chong et al., 2018). Social media can make businesses more

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efficient in developing and managing tourism-related ICT. Cities nowadays compete with one another as urban destinations to maintain the profitable viability of tourism due to greater mobility of people and money (Dinnie, 2011). Social media is an effective tool for businesses in the public and travel industries (Ali & Frew, 2010). Social media has been reaffirmed as a way to distribute and promote products and services (Akehurst, 2009). The ubiquitous use of social media by governments, destination marketers, and tourism authorities helps them adjust their strategies while understanding their markets (Noone et al., 2011). Travellers use social media to make their travelling risk-free (Gretzel et al., 2008). Consumer-generated content (CGC) on social media is determined to be a crucial basis of reliable material by several studies (Xiang et al., 2017). Social media platforms have also allowed travellers to share their travel experiences, influencing other travellers' travel choices. This influence of social media on travellers' decision-making shows their digital belief for this online content (Noone et al., 2011).

Five billion people accessed the internet as of April 2022, making up 63% of the world's population; 4.65 billion people used social media. China, India, and the United States have more internet users than others. As of February 2022, there were over 658 million internet users in India. 3.96 billion users were projected for social networking sites (SNS) by 2022, with these numbers likely to rise as mobile device use and social networks become more common in previously untapped regions. Telecom Regulatory Authority of India reported (2022) that India had 833,710,000 internet users, ranking second in the world behind China, which has 1,010,740,000 internet users. The United States is third, with 312,320,000 internet users (Performance Indicator Report, 2022). Social media impacts travelers' trip-planning behaviour. The more significant social media influence depicts the travellers' digital trust in using travel reviews for their trip-planning decisions. By providing visitors with technologically improved experiences, social media has the ability to elevate destinations to a greater level of sustainability (Chan et al., 2019).

Literature Review

Social media is a class of network apps built on Web 2.0's ideas and technological foundations and allows for the creation and distribution of CGC (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Obar and Wildman (2015) investigated the social media literature further and discovered four distinctive parameters: CGC, Creativity, Interaction, and Web 2.0.

Prior research has revealed a need for consistent social media categorization methods (Chong et al., 2018). Using media research theories and social process theories, Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) categorised social media users into six groups depending on how they used the platform.

Social media and trip planning process : As illustrated in Figure-1, the existing literature (Choe et al., 2017; Fotis et al., 2011) follow generic consumer behaviour theories and models (Woodside & Lyonski, 1989). The trip planning process has been divided into pre, during, and post-trip stages. In the pre-trip stage, travellers understand the desire to travel and begin to analyze their alternatives and look for travel-related information. In the second stage, tourists make distinct buying judgments during their trip. Finally, in the last stage (post-trip), travellers assess their excursions by writing about their experiences on online platforms (Cox et al., 2009). Still, the supreme trip planning stage of using a single platform is yet to be recognized (Ge & Gretzel, 2018; Xiang & Gretzel, 2010). Cox et al. (2009) asserted that social media is mostly utilised for information gathering prior to travel but is hardly ever used while travelling or after returning from a trip. However, Fotis et al. (2011) discovered that social media was primarily utilised to share memories after the trip. Despite the fact that Cox et al. (2009) acknowledged the crucial part social media plays in acquiring knowledge about tourism before travelling. Huang et al. (2010) claimed that social media's primary purpose is to acquire travel-related information. Additionally, Yoo and Gretzel (2010) found that social media is more productive than conventional sources of information for disseminating thorough tourism-related information.

Figure-1 : Process of Travel Planning

Source : Woodside & Lyonski, 1989 and Cox et al., 2009.

According to Tussyadiah and Fesenmaier (2009), social media dramatically impacts trip planning. Fotis et al. (2011) found that prospective travellers are likelier to change their vacation plans as social media influences trip plans. Additionally, Liu et al. (2020) have recently identified some social media roles and functions in the context of travel activities, including supporter and guide. Further research into travel decision-making and technology adoption has been recommended (Liu et al., 2020) and included in the present paper.

Research Gap and Objectives

The trip planning function must be thoroughly investigated (Liu et al., 2020). This supports the claims made by Xiang and Gretzel (2010) and Boley et al. (2013) on social media's role in travellers' searches for trip-related information. It was seen that the function of social media in planning the trips of Indian tourists is still little understood by researchers and practitioners. More theoretical and empirical evidence regarding India's expanding social media usage is required. Even if the influence of social media on travel planning process has been commonly debated, travel markets vary in countless ways across countries (Hajli, 2014). As a result, Fotis et al. (2011) advocated for more studies on individual nations. There is an empirical gap in analyzing the significance and influence of social media on the trip-planning process of Indian travellers (Ráthonyi, 2013). Therefore, bridging this knowledge gap would give tourist marketers more significant opportunities to innovate in social media marketing. Considering these gaps, following objectives have been developed:

- 1) To study the trip-planning behaviour of the tourists
- 2) To determine social media's travel reviews impact on tourists' trip planning.

Methodology

Purposive and snowball sampling have been used. The research design of the paper has been exploratory and descriptive. The sampling unit has been travellers who use social media before planning a trip. Two hundred fifty questionnaires were collected offline between February and May 2022, of which 228 were deemed valid, giving a validity percentage of 91.2%. After a thorough review of the literature, a questionnaire has been created. The perspectives of academics and researchers from the tourism and hospitality industries have been compiled, providing the questionnaire's content validity. There are three sections in this study's questionnaire. The first part of the questionnaire

addressed how people generally arrange their travel plans, including how many trips they take and how long it takes them. The trip planning stages at which travellers use social media have been evaluated in the second part. Next, social media's potential influence on travellers' trip planning has been asked. The third segment evaluated the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. Constructs adopted from prior authors have been: "Number of trips" (Gretzel & Yoo, 2008), "Advance time to plan a trip" (Yoo et al., 2009), "Trip planning stages" (Cox et al., 2009), "Impact of social media on trip planning" (Yoo et al., 2009). Descriptive statistics and Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) have been followed to extract the factors of review significance on trip planning. Next, the significance of travel reviews has been examined for their impact on trip planning using the Logistic Regression model. It has effectively established the causal relationship between independent factors and binary dependent variables (Cheng Hua, 2021). Logistic regression has been utilized as the dependent variable is binary (0 or 1) (Malhotra et al., 2017). The dependent variable has been measured in yes or no (yes = 1, no = 0), while the independent variable has been measured through an interval scale (seven-point Likert scale). The model has been defined as: $L_i = \ln \left(\frac{P_i}{1 - P_i} \right) = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, \dots, X_k)$ where, $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$, P_i = probability of occurrence of an event, $1 - P_i$ = probability of non-occurrence, L_i = dependent variable, and X_i = independent variable,.

Results

Respondents' Profiles : Most respondents were females (53.5%) compared to males (46.5%). The maximum number of respondents aged 31-40 (36%) in comparison to 21-30 (21.9%), 41-50 (26.3%) and 51 and above (15.8%). The education level of the respondents has been post-graduation (49.1%), graduation (46.1%), and secondary school (4.8%). The annual family income in descending order has been 6 to less than 10 lakh (46.1%), 3 - less than 6 lakh (26.3%), 10 and above (21.1 %), and less than 3 lakh (6.5%).

Number of trips & advance time of trip planning : Significantly higher share of respondents (51.3%) have travelled 1-2 times, 3-4 times (40.8%), 5-6 times (3.9%), and 7-8 times (2.6%). In contrast, no respondent reported for 9 or more times. Next, advance time of trip planning was considered, where 38.2% of respondents had begun planning their vacations one to less than three weeks in advance, 23.7% three to less than eight weeks, 16.7% 2 to less than 4 months, 10.5 % 1-6 days in advance, 7% 6 or more months in advance, and 2.6% during the trip, and 1.3% have used social media for trip planning 4 to less than 6 months.

Information sources used for trip planning : Social media sites (80%) have been the significant information source, followed by the reviews of fellow travellers (70%) and friends and relatives (46%), travel guide book/magazine (45%), official websites of the destination (37%), travel agents (35%) whereas tv/radio/newspapers (32%) have been the least imperative among these sources.

Stages of travel planning process : According to mean scores of the three stages, social media has often been employed in the first stage (pre-trip) of trip planning (mean = 5.32) in comparison to the during-trip stage (mean = 5.09) and post-trip stage (mean = 4.85). In the pre-trip stage, social media has been chiefly utilized to seek information on accommodation possibilities (mean = 5.75) and to screen out attraction options (mean = 5.53). The lowest mean score of 4.86 was for destination search options and 5.14 for screening choices of destination. At the during-trip stage, people have primarily utilized social media to get material about a particular holiday activity (mean = 5.47), and connect with their friends (mean = 5.36). Lowest mean score of 4.56 has been provided to develop a relationship with other travellers on social media. Next, social media has been extensively utilized in the last stage (post-trip) to share videos/images with their friends (mean = 5.32), followed by providing reviews about their travel experience (mean = 5.03). However, social media has been used less at this stage to get inspiration for the next trip (mean = 4.32).

Influence of online travel reviews on trip planning : To study the fundamental driving elements influencing the significance of travel reviews, principal component analysis (PCA) with varimax rotation was calculated to analyze the impacts of online reviews on the planning of the travellers. The analysis has identified six factors with significant factor loadings, accounting for 73.379% of the total variation across twenty-four variables. The Kaiser-Meyer Oklin (K.M.O.) sample adequacy score (0.727) and Bartlett's test were also significant ($X^2 = 3218.421$, $p = 0.000$). The dependability of these parameters has been analyzed to establish the degree of scale consistency, which has been greater than the allowed level of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2009). The factors include Idea/Information Generation, Compare Alternatives, Fun Activity, Surge Efficiency, Risk Reduction, and Safe Travel, and The first factor (Idea/Information Generation) covered eight variables with factor loadings as : 'Travel reviews help me to learn about a travel destination (0.793)', 'I seek ideas on best time/season to travel (0.752)', 'I find more information about a destination that I had already planned to go (0.722)', 'I get to learn from others' experiences (0.681)', 'Travel reviews help to imagine trips more vividly (0.665)', 'I can easily imagine what the place

will be like (0.631)', 'I get a clear idea of what to expect from my trip (0.558)', 'Travel reviews provides ideas for my trip (0.568)'. The explanatory power of this factor was 22.79%, with an Eigenvalue of 6.34 and a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.87. The second factor (*Fun Activity*) comprised three items: 'Travel reviews make my planning more enjoyable (0.710)', 'Travel reviews add fun to the planning (0.686)', and 'I feel more excited about traveling after reading travel reviews (0.569)'. This factor explains 16.46% of the variance with an Eigenvalue of 5.17 and a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.84. The third factor, *Compare Alternatives*, includes: 'I can evaluate different alternatives for accommodation (0.708)', 'I can evaluate different alternatives of attractions/leisure activities and select the best option (0.707)', and 'I can evaluate different alternatives for destination and select the best option out of them (0.587)'. This factor has contributed 12.39% to explaining the variations, 4.52 Eigenvalue, and Cronbach's alpha of 0.753. The fourth factor (*Surge Efficiency*) covered- 'Travel reviews save time in planning my trip (0.801)', 'Travel reviews help to plan trips efficiently (0.676)', and 'Travel reviews help me to reach a decision (0.663)'. The Eigenvalue of this factor was 3.41, and it explains 8.12% of variance with Cronbach's Alpha of 0.87. The fifth factor (*Safe Travel*) covered – 'To know whether safety norms are followed at accommodations/hotels during this pandemic (0.828)', 'To know which destination is safe to travel to during a pandemic (0.755)', and 'To know whether safety norms are followed at destinations during this time of pandemic (0.503)'. The Eigenvalue of this factor was 2.16, and it explains 6.38% of the variance with Cronbach's alpha of 0.76. The sixth factor (*Risk Reduction*) covered: 'Travel reviews help to avoid services I would not enjoy (0.869)', 'Travel reviews reduce the risk involved in travel decisions (0.852)', 'Reduce the likelihood, I will later regret (0.802)', and 'Travel reviews increase confidence in decision-making (0.670)'. The Eigenvalue of this factor was 1.45, and it explains 4.77% of the variance with Cronbach's alpha of 0.83.

For confirmatory factor analysis results, factor loading of each variable was greater than 0.6, demonstrating internal consistency and convergent validity (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988). The average variance recovered for these constructs was larger than 0.50, and Cronbach's alpha value for each factor was more than 0.70, showing composite reliability. The model has substantial fit indices (CMIN/D.F. = 3.010, NFI = 0.902, TLI = 0.917, AGFI = 0.911, GFI = 0.927, RMSEA = 0.045, $p = 0.000$).

Figure-2 : Measurement Model

(Author's elaboration)

Results of Logistic Regression : The respondents who have changed their trip plan have been classified as 1, and those who did not made changes have been coded as 0. The model's fit was then tested using omnibus tests of its coefficients, which indicated a significant value of 0.000, showing model fits well. Similarly, the Hosmer and Lemeshow test has reported a value of 0.832, more than the required value of 0.05 (Hosmer et al., 2013), which shows that the model correctly described the data. Next, the pseudo-R-square has also been utilized as an approximation variation in the criteria variable. Nagelkerke's R^2 , a modified version of the Cox & Snell R^2 , reported a 14.2% variation in the criterion variable accredited to the model's predictor variables. The overall model adequately categorized 66.7% of cases; this shows the percentage of correct categorization in circumstances where it is anticipated that respondents may alter their trip plans. The percentages have revealed the 38.8% specificity and 83.2% sensitivity of the model when attempting to predict group membership based on the dependent variable (Malhotra et al., 2017). The overall accuracy percentage has been 66.7%, which is quite excellent. 83.3% of people who made modifications based on the model have been accurately predicted compared to those who did not; the model shows strong sensitivity.

Table 1: Equation variables

Factors	Xi	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I.for EXP(B)	
								Lower	Upper
Idea/Information Generation	X1	.322	.334	.928	1	.335	1.380	1.217	2.657
Fun Activity	X2	.835	.240	12.060	1	.001	1.434	1.271	1.695
Compare Alternatives	X3	.486	.250	3.763	1	.052	1.615	1.376	1.705
Surge Efficiency	X4	.737	.241	9.379	1	.002	2.091	1.304	3.351
Safe Travel	X5	.150	.205	.532	1	.466	1.161	1.107	1.736
Risk Reduction	X6	.349	.182	3.653	1	.056	1.706	1.493	1.809
Constant		2.950	1.588	3.452	1	.063	19.098		

(Source: Based on primary data)

The model written as: $Li = 2.950 + .322X1 + .835X2 + .486X3 + .737X4 + .150X5 + .349X6$

Next, the correlation between the predictors and the result is displayed in Table 1. Here, (B) denotes the anticipated change in log odds, which indicates that for every unit change in the predictor; the likelihood of the result will vary by Exp (B). For X1, the odds of travellers making changes in their trip plans are 1.380 times higher than those who did not make changes when they got ideas for their trips. This implies that the factor 'Idea/Information Generation' is significant in the probability of an event occurring, i.e., to make changes in travellers' initial trip plans. Similar is the case with other factors, i.e., X2, X3, X4, X5, and X6, as their odds ratio is also greater than 1, i.e., 1.434, 1.615, 2.091, and 1.161, respectively. Hence, these factors significantly influence the trip planning of travellers. Also, the p-values of factors 'Fun Activity' and 'Surge Efficiency' are less than 0.05, which shows that these variables significantly impacts trip planning of the travellers in contrast to other factors, i.e., 'Idea/Information Generation' (X1), 'Compare Alternatives' (X3), 'Safe Travel' (X5), and 'Risk Reduction' (X6) as the p-value of these factors is greater than 0.05. These factors have an influential role in impacting the trip-planning decisions of travellers.

Discussion

It has been seen through the results of the data analysis that travellers are very cautious while planning their trips. Concerning the information sources used for trip planning, it has been seen that the services a particular social media provides influence its selection and usage. Some social network applications focus on more specific purposes, such as information search, travel reviews,

experience and narrative sharing, and general factual platforms. Users have specified and defined a clear offering of travel-related services. Rather than downloading only one or two applications, travellers install and use many social networking platforms simultaneously. Furthermore, multi-functional social media platforms have been increasingly popular among users. These platforms are primarily utilized during the pre-trip stage for collecting information, as indicated by Cox et al. (2009). Social media sites, reviews of other travellers from travel review websites have been the extensively used information sources. It may be attributed to the reason that social media is overloaded with the latest information, which has been written by an ordinary man from the customer's point of view since ordinary people have no selfish interest while posting such information in contrast to marketers, who have profit-related interests. As per the usage of online platforms at various stages of trip planning, it was found that social media has been extensively utilised at the first stage (pre-trip) to seek ideas for the destination, lodging, and other leisure activities. This finding has been similar with the prior research (Cox et al., 2009; Yuan et al., 2022), which suggested that most travellers look for other accommodation choices via travel reviews after deciding on a particular destination. The reason behind the maximum use of social media in the pre-trip stage is that travellers seek new ideas for their trips. Also, to minimize the risk involved in trip planning, travellers try to collect every unit of information from different social media platforms before their trips. Additionally, it has been observed that social media has been utilised chiefly to search for lodging-related information at the pre-trip stage. It implies that travellers do not want to take the hassle of finding hotels at their destination later. It would be a waste of time and involve the risk of inefficient services, which could have been avoided otherwise. At the same time, social media was minimally used for searching for ideas about the destination at the pre-trip stage. It might be because travellers had decided to visit a specific destination in advance from other sources such as friends, TV, or past experience. At the during-trip stage, social media has been extensively utilized to seek ideas about leisure activities. It might be attributed to the reason that to explore the destination and to have a better experience; travellers try to visit the specific attractions and places of the particular destination. Further, in post-trip stage, social media has been utilized for the maximum time for sharing their trip photos/videos with friends and other travelers. This outcome has been consistent with that of Yuan et al. (2022). It is because people relive their trip while sharing their photos/videos on social media. It is a sharing their experience with their known.

According to PCA findings, social media has been utilized for six new reasons in India, including Idea/Information Generation, Risk Reduction, Fun Activity, Compare Alternatives, Safe Travel, and Surge Efficiency. The first factor (Idea/Information Generation) describes that travellers often use social media to get new ideas about destination choices, accommodation choices, and leisure activities. Travellers also use social media to get a vivid idea of what their trip will be all about. Hence, travellers try to extract maximum information from social media. The second factor (Fun Activity) depicts that travel reviews adds fun to the travelling experience. The travellers could easily explore different trip options, making this process more enjoyable. The third factor (Compare Alternatives) implies that social media is overloaded with travel information, providing immense information and options for travellers to evaluate the options and select the best out of them. The fourth factor (Surge Efficiency) describes that travel reviews on different social media platforms help travellers quickly decide from the various alternatives, which fastens the trip planning process. Hence, this readily available information on social media saves the time and effort of travellers. The fifth factor (Safe Travel) describes that information regarding various safety norms being followed at the destination and accommodation during the pandemic can be searched from various social media platforms. This helps the travellers to ensure their safety and health concerns. The sixth factor (Risk Reduction) implies that travel reviews help travellers to reduce the uncertainty involved in the trip planning process. Since services offered at the destination and accommodation cannot be felt in advance, the travellers could read the reviews provided by other travellers for various services on social media platforms.

Next, the empirical results of Logistic Regression have demonstrated that the extracted factors are influential factors in altering the trip planning of travellers. This implies that most travellers read travel reviews for ideas or information about the destination, accommodation, or other leisure activities. Due to this, the travellers might alter their travel plans. Similarly, travellers consider travel reviews to add fun to their trips. They compare different alternatives and choose the best to get better trip experiences. Also, travellers make every effort to minimize the cost of travelling and maximize the benefits. In this way, travellers can increase the efficiency of their trip. Furthermore, travellers make every effort to ensure safety at the destination and accommodation, which is the fundamental reason behind considering other travellers' reviews in their trip planning, particularly post-COVID. Hence, the extracted factors are influential in impacting the trip planning of travellers.

Theoretical / Research Implications

This research has filled a knowledge gap by examining the impact of travel review significance on travellers' travel plans. The findings have established the cause-effect nature of the link between travel review significance predictors and travel planning. The research's conclusions have called for diversifying the methods people use to access social media pre, during, and after travel. Further, scholarly research on the distinct effect of social media platforms is required for how fragmented and localized the Indian social media market is. Next, using data mining and big data tools to explore how CGC from social media affects travellers' behaviour, innovation, and destination sustainability is required. It is essential to comprehend how much CGC contributes to the economy, destination image, and local communities, among other facets of sustainable tourism futures. Also, specific strategies for particular user categories should be carefully examined when making policy sanctions for urban destinations or concrete ramifications in the tourist industry.

Managerial / Practical Implications

Considering the digital trust for social media to increase the number of visits to a website, it is essential to include the relevant social media platforms in marketing initiatives. For instance, tourist marketers should successfully promote relevant information on the associated platforms while identifying the separation of social media duties (e.g., self-directed sources of agents on micro blogs, blogs, and SNS; direct product-oriented promotion on commercial travel groups). As travellers do not obtain information from a single source, they gather information from numerous sources to extract more information and reduce travel risk. Hence, CGC has to be managed more effectively and integrated into more extensive systems of smart tourist destinations, as the deluge of information on online platforms may put the authenticity and dependability of such sources under scrutiny.

Research Limitations and Scope of Future Research

By comparing pre- and post-COVID perspectives, more research must be done to recognize the social media usage on shifting behaviour of travellers. Secondly, thorough interviews can be conducted to evaluate the theoretical model's applicability using extensive quantitative data analysis and cross-national comparison.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study's results have revealed how Indian travellers use social media to plan their vacations and the potential for innovative thinking to influence the tourist industry. Tourists use various online platforms, including SNS and travel review websites, to plan their trips. These platforms have enabled more varied functions of information provision and social networking. This research has scientifically evaluated this tendency, which also looks at the trip-planning behaviour of travellers. The results of this study have concluded that people are risk-averse. By lowering the likelihood of risk and uncertainty associated with trip planning, people attempt to optimize money and time efficiency. Particularly after COVID-19, people have been increasingly concerned about their safety. Hence, the study of post-COVID travellers' trip planning behaviour is highly recommended to understand the probable shift in their general trip planning behaviour, where the variables of this study could be studied comparatively to the two scenarios, i.e., pre- and post-COVID. Lastly, this research has shown how social media contributes to sustainable tourism through a quantitative analysis of travellers' social media use.

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